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Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis of Urban Sprawl in Solapur City A Geographical Analysis

Dr. Raghavendra V. Tatipamul

Abstract

The characteristic features of a city are the result of the combination of various factors like topography, climate, history, economy and culture etc. since these characteristics vary, and very town/city is unique and has a certain distinctive characteristics. These urban characteristics are however never static. They change both over time and space. With the development of the economy other factors, like population growth, urbanization and improved technology have a combined effect on urban settlements, which grow bigger and more complex. Urban sprawl is a common phenomenon in every growing city. Urban researchers are now focusing to study urban sprawl and its impact. The term Urban Sprawl describing the physical pattern of low density expansion of larger urban areas under market conditions into the surrounding agricultural areas. Sprawl lies in advance of the principal lines of urban growth and implies little planning control of land subdivision. The present paper discussed about urban sprawl of Solapur city. To calculate urban sprawl and land use land cover change is done by using satellite imageries. Multiple ring buffer analysis is frequently used for study urban sprawl. Urban sprawl is studied by various methods but multiple ring buffer technique is used for detection of pattern of sprawl. Key Words: Urban sprawl, Remote Sensing, GIS, Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis, Leapfrog pattern

Introduction

Urban sprawl is very common phenomena in growing city. Urbanization affects on population size, which impacts on built up area. The built up area is increased due to population growth, increasing commercial activities, CBD extension and city development plans etc. The present paper is focusing on urban sprawl pattern with the help of multiple ring buffer analysis technique.

Objectives

The present study has certain specific objectives. It includes studying multiple ring buffer analysis of urban sprawl of solapur city.

Study Area

The Solapur city is one of the fastest growing cities in Maharashtra. It is Headquarter of Solapur District. The total area of study area is 178.5 Sq.Km. The city is bounded by 16 villages. According to 2007 and 2011 the Population of city was estimated 977162 and 1133009 respectively. After the 1992 extension number of villages included in Solapur city.

Fig 1.1

Database and Methodology

The present study covering an entire city as the study area. The present work includes measuring built up area with the use of satellite images. The LANDSAT TM 1992, LANDSAT ETM+ 2002 and IRS P6 LISS III 2012 images collected from NRSA. The secondary data collected from census of India, published by the directorate of economics and statistics, Government of Maharashtra, District census handbook, Gazetteers. The collected data and images processed with GIS software.

Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis of Solapur City

Multiple ring buffering is an important method for analysis of urban sprawl pattern. To analysis urban sprawl and its pattern, 11 rings were created. Every ring distance interval of 1000 m has been created from city centre point. Centre point is selected with the reference of Google earth. Table 5.2 and fig 5.6, 5.7 and 5.8 shows multiple ring buffer analysis. The multiple ring buffer analysis detected the leapfrog pattern of urban sprawl of Solapur city. The built up area covered in 0-1000m ring was 2.46 sq.km, 2.61sq.km and 2.95 sq.km in 1992, 2002, and 2012 respectively. The first ring has unavailable of open space for growth. This ring is covered core area of city. The area covered other than built up are open grounds, garden and water tank. The ring 1000-2000 m covered 7.00, 7.26 and 7.78 sq.km in 1992, 2002, and 2012 respectively. The first two rings are devoted for only commercial purpose. Vertical growth of city observed in first and second ring. There is restriction of horizontal expansion of city area in 0-2000 m ring. The residential area is very low in first two rings. The third and fourth ring have the area under residential is very high as compare other rings. The highest built up area covered in 2000-3000 m ring is 8.79, 10.18 and 11.97 sq.km in 1992, 2002, and 2012 respectively. The 3000-4000 m ring covered 4.62, 6.27, 9.70 sq.km in 1992, 2002 and 2012 respectively. The built up area is very high in third and fourth ring, because this area has scope for horizontal expansion of urban area. Also land value is low compare to core area. The first four ring covered total built up area was 22.87, 26.32sq.km and 32.4 sq.km in 1992, 2002 and 2012 respectively. The built area covered between 4000 to 9000 m was 3.17, 4.95 and 8.93 sq.km in 1992, 2002 and 2012 respectively. In the year 1992, there is absence of built up area in 9000-10000 m and 10000-11000 m. In 2002 and 2012, there is slightly increased built up area in 9000-10000 m. In the year 2002 and 2012, built area was constant in 10000-11000 m ring, i.e. 0.01sq.km. The built up area is continuously increasing from 0-1000 m to 2000-3000 m ring. After five rings the patches of built up area is observed in interval of some distances in all direction. It shows the leapfrog pattern of urban sprawl.

The city built up area directional expansion is complex. Built up area increasing maximum in the south east. Patches of built up area also observed in the north west side. City built up area also extended in north east side.

Table 1.1
Built-Up Area (sq.km) Covered in Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis of Solapur City

Distance in meters	1992	2002	2012
0-1000	2.46	2.61	2.95
1000-2000	7.00	7.26	7.78
2000-3000	8.79	10.18	11.97
3000-4000	4.62	6.27	9.70
4000-5000	1.78	2.80	4.48
5000-6000	0.80	1.20	2.49
6000-7000	0.49	0.72	1.42
7000-8000	0.02	0.08	0.33
8000-9000	0.08	0.15	0.21
9000-10000	0.00	0.07	0.34
10000-11000	0.00	0.01	0.01
Total	26.03	31.34	41.69

Source: Computed by Researcher.

Fig 1.2

Source: Classified Image Prepared by Researcher.

Fig 1.3

Source: Classified Image Prepared by Researcher.

Fig 1.4

Source Classified Image Prepared by Researcher.

Conclusion

1. The multiple ring buffer analysis is detected patches of built up area distance from core area. This pattern of study area is experiencing leapfrog pattern of sprawl.
2. The built up area is spread over the entire buffer ring in study area except in 1992.
3. The built up area decreasing from centre to outside area of solapur city.
4. The multiple ring buffer from 0-4000 m covers above the 50 % built up area of city.
5. The highest built up area shown in the 2000 m-3000 m ring are 8.79, 10.18 and 11.97sq.km in 1992, 2002 and 2012 respectively.
6. The directional expansion of urban sprawl is observed in the north east, south east and North West side.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

References

1. **Alam.S.M.**(1965), Hyderabad-Secunderabad twin cities- A study in urban geography. Allied Publishers.
2. **Barnes, K.B., Morgan, III, J.M., Roberge, M.C., Lowe, S.** (2001). Sprawl Development: Its Patterns, Consequences, and Measurement. Towson University, Towson.
3. **Belser, K.** (1960). Urban dispersal in perspective, in *The Nature and Control of Urban Dispersal* Ed. E A Engelbert, California Chapter of the American Institute of Planners, Berkeley, CA, pp 18.
4. **Datta K.L** (1967), Urban zones of India, National Geographical Journal of India.
5. **Draft development plan of Solapur** (1996). Including revision of the sanctioned development plans report I, II, III SMC.
6. **Ewing, R.** (1994). Characteristics, causes, and effects of sprawl: a literature review. *Environmental and Urban Issues*. 21, pp 15.
7. **Haregewoin Bekele** (2005). Urbanization and Urban Sprawl. Master of Science Thesis No. 294, Stockholm.
8. **K. Siddhartha** (2000), Cities urbanization and urban system, Kishalayya pub. PVT, New Delhi.
9. **Khatib K. A.** (2007) Settlement geography, Mehata publishing house, Kolhapur.
10. **Knowles R and Wareing J** (1976) Economic and social geography, Heinemann professional books, London.
11. **Lewis P.**(1972), Small towns in Pennsylvania, *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*.
12. **Murphy R.** (1954), The City as a center of change western Europe and China, *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*.
13. **R.C. Tiwari** (2020), Settlement Geography, Pravalika Publication, Prayagraj.
14. **Stewart C.T.** (1947), The Size and Spacing of Cities, *Geographical Review*.
15. **World Population prospects** (2002). The 2012 revision, volume I, compressive tables, United Nations, New York.